

Latest results from XENONnT and prospects for the future

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On behalf of the XENON collaboration

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XENON Collaboration

- **180** scientists, **30** institutions, **12** countries
- Based at Laboratori Nazionale del Gran Sasso (**LNGS**)
- Uses dual phase xenon TPC
- XENONnT primary physics goal is to search for **dark matter (WIMP) nucleon interactions**

XENONnT Dual Phase TPC

S1 and S2 signals together are used to:

- Perform energy reconstruction
- Reconstruct three dimensional position of events
- Discriminate between Electronic Recoils (ER) and Nuclear Recoils (NR)

XENONnT experiment

~10x10m
water tank

Muon
Veto

Depth 1400m
(3800m w/e)

Capable of
searching for
rare event
processes

Rn/Kr
distillation

Neutron
veto

DAQ/Slow
Control

TPC

Capable of
detecting
nuclear recoils
down to
~1keV

Gd loaded
water

Liquid
purification

Solar neutrino signals

Solar neutrinos induce events from both nuclear and electronic recoils in our detector

Further opportunity to examine rare-event processes and do some neutrino physics!

L. E. Strigari, New J. Phys. 11, 105011 (2009)

Boron-8 neutrinos (Nuclear Recoil)

Coherent Elastic Neutrino-Nucleus Scattering - $CE\nu NS$ (neutrino is scattering from the nucleus as a whole - N^2 enhancement).

Exactly as we would like to detect WIMPs!

Process measured by COHERENT in 2017 with reactor neutrinos

Approximate NR threshold

SR0 + SR1

LXe Purification

- Electron Lifetime > 10 ms - we need to see signals!
- Eur. Phys. J. C 77 (2017) 275
- Eur. Phys. J. C 82 (2022) 860

Triggerless DAQ

- DAQ shared between three detectors
- Improve low-energy sensitivity
- JINST 18, P07054 (2023)

Exposure of around 3.5 t.yr

Boron-8 neutrinos (Nuclear Recoil)

In XENONnT the amount of energy deposited is very small! >90% less than 2.1keV!

PMT coincidence threshold of 2

Neutron calibration from ^{88}YBe source

Dedicated inference space developed.

Expected Background: 26.4 ± 1.5 ← From radioactive backgrounds and accidentals!

Expected Signal: 12 ± 3

Events Observed: **37**

-> Consistent with $10.7^{+3.7}_{-4.3}$ events

[Phys. Rev. Lett. 133, 191002](#)

Solar neutrinos (Electronic recoil)

PP neutrinos are undetectable from nuclear recoils in XENONnT - but they are possible by electronic recoils!

Need to understand the backgrounds from Rn and Kr as well as materials!

Low rate!

[Phys. Rev. Lett. 129, 161805](#)

Low energy!

Analysis considerations

Continuous Rn online distillation

- ^{222}Rn SR0 : 1.9 $\mu\text{Bq/kg}$
- ^{222}Rn SR1 : 0.9 $\mu\text{Bq/kg}$
- Eur. Phys. J. C 82 (2022) 1104

Kr distillation

- natKr/Xe concentration < 50 ppq
- Monitor with a Rare Gas Mass Spectrometer(RGMS)

LXe Purification

- Electron Lifetime > 10 ms
- Eur. Phys. J. C 77 (2017) 275
- Eur. Phys. J. C 82 (2022) 860

Triggerless DAQ

- DAQ shared between three detectors
- Improve low-energy sensitivity
- JINST 18, P07054 (2023)

Material Screening

- Eur. Phys. J. C 82, 599 (2022)

At solar neutrino level!

Analysis here is ongoing! Results will hopefully come soon!

Phys. Rev. X 15, 031079

XENONnT Upgrade

Drift field has limited the performance of the experiment ->Upgrade necessary!

A wire had broken on the bottom screening mesh creating an electrical short.

Cathode replaced (hexagonal mesh).
Anode and gate also replaced

Considerable work needed from tpc and veto teams to undertake work

Re-commissioning is about to begin!

Future prospects

The upgraded detector will have advanced background rejection capabilities as well as enhanced signal detection capabilities.

Enhancement of signal over background close to threshold will enhance the abilities to detect ^8B solar neutrinos.

Further exposure also enhances the detection capabilities of ER solar neutrinos - these are irreducible backgrounds for other science searches

XENONnT: The Smallest Solar Neutrino Detector

Slide courtesy: R. Hammann

Thank You!

Backup

Detector characterisation

^{220}Rn - mainly a flat ^{212}Pb spectrum used to measure the ER response and efficiencies

AmBe - neutron source used to measure NR response. Tagged events from 4.4 MeV γ -ray observed in the NV.

Other Sources:

^{83}mKr for detector characterisation, LED (fibres)

References:

Signal reconstruction, calibration and event selection

Phys. Rev. D 111 (2025) 062006

Signal and background modelling and statistical inference

Phys. Rev. D 111 (2025) 103040

SR0 + SR1 Backgrounds - WIMP search

Accidental contamination with 'offgas'

Distillation removes most Kr

[PRD 111, 103040 \(2025\)](#)

SR0 + SR1 WIMP search efficiencies

SR0 + SR1 WIMP search

Unbinned likelihood.
Separable for SR0 and SR1. Near and far wire regions were also modelled separately.

Analysis was blinded for SR1 (SR0 was already published)

No excess observed

FIG. 4. Upper limits on the SI WIMP-nucleon cross section (90% CL) as a function of the WIMP mass (black line). The sensitivity band is indicated by the region containing 68% (green shaded) and 95% (yellow shaded) of expected upper limits under the background-only hypothesis as well as their median (dotted line). In addition, we show published results from XENONnT using only SR0 data [3], LZ [4], and PandaX-4T [5]. For all, a PCL with a power threshold of 0.16 is used (XENONnT SR0 limit recast accordingly).

PP-neutrinos - XENON and XLZD

- Measurement of ν_e survival probability (P_{e-e})
- Measurement for the Weinberg angle at low Q
- Search for exotic neutrino interactions (ex. Magnetic moment)
- XENONnT has some sensitivity, but XLZD should ultimately be able to measure this

[J. Phys. G: Nucl. Part. Phys. 50 013001](#)

[Eur. Phys. J. C 85, 1192 \(2025\)](#)

Figure 30. Running of the Weinberg angle $\sin^2 \theta_w$ as a function of momentum scale Q^2 , along with measured values. A deviation from SM predictions (black line) could indicate the presence of new physics effects. The green band indicates the effect of a new Z' with $m_{Z'} = 50$ MeV, where the width of the band is determined by the strength of the kinetic mixing parameter with $U(1)_Y$. An $\mathcal{O}(\text{tonne-year})$ xenon dark matter observatory can extend the reach of these measurements down to the keV scale, significantly to the left of this plot, via the measurement of the pp solar neutrino flux. Reprinted (figure) with permission from [861], Copyright (2014) by the American Physical Society.

Colourised photo
